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Opinionated Covid Conspiracies In Pakistan's Newspapers: A Cada Approach

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Abstract: *The purpose of the present research is to analyze opinion articles in Pakistani newspapers Dawn and The News for presenting COVID-19 related conspiracy theories. COVID-19 triggered a wide range of discourses in the media, with conspiracy theories gaining particular prominence. Newspapers, as major opinion-shaping platforms, played a crucial role in circulating and framing such narratives. A total of 263 opinion articles were collected using Python's library and annotated against four prominent groups of conspiracies, namely origin, spread, control/cure, and portrayal/beliefs. Out of these, 194 articles were identified as containing conspiracies. The study employed a Corpus-Assisted Discourse Analysis (CADA) approach to examine the annotated corpus. The findings reveal that both Dawn and The News shared significantly related vocabulary and somewhat similar phrasings. However, Dawn contained more conspiracy-laden articles than The News, with a greater tendency toward politically inclined conspiracies, while The News focused more on health-oriented conspiracies. It is recommended that future research should conduct more in-depth journalistic and linguistic analysis with larger and more representative datasets to better understand the ideological dimensions of conspiracy discourses in the media.*

Keywords: *conspiracy theories, COVID-19, linguistic analysis, discourse analysis, Pakistani, English newspapers*

Introduction

Conspiracy theories have been extensively studied across various disciplines, including journalism, history, psychology, sociology, philosophy, communication, social media, and anthropology (Stieger et al., 2013; Graumann, 1987; Abalakina-Paap et al., 1999; Harambam and Aupers, 2017; Coady, 2006; Southwell et al., 2018; Greenberg et al., 2017; Rousseau and Jamil, 2008). The outbreak of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) not only brought a global pandemic but also a surge in conspiracy theories surrounding its origin, spread, prevention, effect etc. Conspiracy theories, while not exclusive to scientific contexts, have a significant impact on trust in scientific research, particularly during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. Studies have shown that people tend to believe in conspiracies during societal crises as they seek explanatory compasses for their attitudes and

behaviours, ultimately reducing perceived uncertainty (van Prooijen & Douglas, 2017; Douglas et al., 2017). Consequently, investigating the language used to spread conspiracies becomes crucial in understanding their effects on belief systems. Historically, language has been overlooked in conspiracy research, as highlighted by editors in previous works (Demata et al., 2022). However, more recent studies have focused on the linguistic aspect of conspiracies and specifically explored discourse patterns (Klein et al., 2018; Bjerg and Presskorn-Thygesen, 2017; Clementson, 2016; Ekram et al., 2019; Takaoka, 2019; Brugnoti et al., 2019). Building upon this growing interest, the present research aims to contribute to the less explored dimension of conspiracy theories. Specifically, this paper delves into the language of conspiracies within the context of Pakistani English newspaper opinion articles corpora. By exploring the linguistic characteristics of conspiracy-related content, this research seeks to explore the use of language.

Research Gap

Before COVID-19, most of the conspiracy research revolved around war (Uscinski and Parent, 2014), politics (Anderson, 1996), deaths/assassination of public figures or related events (Harding and Stewart, 2003; Marcus, 1999). However, Covid-19 shifted the trend, significance and impact of conspiracies and plethora of research has been carried out targeting COVID-19 conspiracy from different perspectives, not limited to, network analysis (Tangherlini et al., 2020), beliefs in COVID-19 theories (Uscinski et al., 2020), conspiracy's impact on the policing for lockdown (Duffy and Allington, 2020). Also, various papers presented different conspiracies after social media, online discussion forums or newspaper analysis. Marcellino et al. (2021) presented most detailed conspiracy theory analysis related to COVID-19 posts on social media where they categorized alien visitation, the danger of vaccinations, the origin of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), and the possibility of white genocide (WG) as the broader categories of many specific categories. However, conspiracies in Pakistani context are yet to be investigated septicly from linguistic and journalistic perspective.

Research Objectives

- To collect the corpus of COVID-19 Newspaper opinion articles.
- To annotate the COVID-19 Newspaper opinion articles
- To analyse the annotated COVID-19 Newspaper opinion articles.

Limitations

- The annotation in the present research is carried out by the researcher only.
- Due to the limitation of time, the present research relied on limited number of articles publish between a specific date.
- Limited number of COVID-19 conspiracies were involved in the present research, and they were gathered in only four clusters.

Literature Review

The following review firstly presents definition of conspiracy and studies conducted in different disciplines i.e., communication, history, philosophy, psychology, and linguistics. Afterwards, the literature dwells into discussing studies related to COVID-19 and conspiracies in diverse contexts including Pakistan.

Although conspiracy theories have been studied within numerous disciplines offering insights into their cognitive foundations, historical origins, psychological influences, and communication dynamics, it still lacks a consensus towards its definition. According to some researchers, conspiracy theory is a sub-

type of rumour (Kou et al., 2017). Some associate it with the individual's trying to attain specific goals without being highlighted (Martin, 2020; Dentith, 2014). Others explain conspiracy theories as conflicting narratives in comparison to the mainstream narratives (Martin, 2020; Uscinski, 2020). The following paragraphs present definitions of conspiracies from diverse fields.

Keeley (1999) studied conspiracies from philosophical perspective and defined conspiracies as “A proposed explanation of some historical event (or events) in terms of the significant causal agency of a relatively small group of persons – the conspirators – acting in secret”. Sunstein and Vermeule (2009) offered their definition of conspiracy from the political perspective and presented conspiracy as an “Effort to explain some event or practice by reference to the machinations of powerful people, who attempt to conceal their role (at least until their aims are accomplished).” From the communication research perspective, Banas and Miller (2013) defined conspiracy as “Causal narratives of an event as a covert plan orchestrated by a secret cabal of people or organisations instead of a random or natural happening.” March & Springer (2019) explained conspiracies from the psychological perspective. According to them conspiracy is an “Alternative explanations of an event involving a conspirator plot organised by powerful people or organisations.” Following this Douglas et al. (2019) added political aspect to the psychological explanation and defined conspiracy as “Attempts to explain the ultimate causes of significant social and political events and circumstances with claims of secret plots by two or more powerful actors.” Lastly and more recently, Intornee et al. (2020) carried out linguistics research to detect conspiracies through machine learning techniques and according to them conspiracy is “a narrative explaining an event or series of events that involve deceptive, coordinated actors working together to achieve a goal through an action or series of actions that have consequences that intentionally disenfranchise or harm an individual or population.”

All these definitions presented within different disciplines have regarded conspiracy as an explanation of an event, but the type of event is distinct among all these definitions i.e., historical event (Keeley, 1999), causal narrative (Banas & Miller, 2013), causes of social and political events (Douglas et al., 2019) and narrative that explains event or series of events (Intornee et al., 2020). Another important characteristic that is present in most of the definitions is that conspiracy is carried out by powerful people (Sunstein & Vermeule, 2009; March & Springer, 2019; Douglas et al., 2019) attempting to maintain, conceal or gain power. These definitions also reflect that conspiracy is a planned activity instead of a random that revolves around a plot or narrative presented by the conspirator and that plot might be a secret. The present research follows the definition presented by Intornee et al. (2020) and considers that events associated with related to COVID-19 are explained by different actors with a specific aim through the spread of information that is harmful for the society as well as an individual.

Historical studies have traced the evolution of conspiracy theories over time (Klausnitzer 2007; Butter 2014). While earlier historians rarely analysed conspiracy theories explicitly, they often presented conspiracist interpretations of historical events. The twentieth century witnessed a surge in historical research on conspiracies, with notable works focusing on events like the French Revolution (Cochin 1909), the New England Illuminati scare of the 1790s (Stauffer 1918), and the origins of the First World War (Beard 1936). Contemporary historians have expanded their investigations across various historical eras and regions, leading to an exponential growth of historical research on conspiracy theories (Pagán 2004; Roisman 2006; Zwierlein 2013; Hof 2013; McKenzie-McHarg 2019).

Conspiracy thinking has also been explored by researchers in philosophy (Keeley 1999; Dentith 2014; Cohnitz 2017; Cassam 2019). Their investigations have identified reasoning errors that typify conspiracy thinking, shedding light on the mechanisms that contribute to the formation and dissemination of conspiracy theories and a starting point to work with the warranted and unwarranted conspiracies. Researchers have also explored the psychological factors that contribute to conspiracy endorsement (Goertzel 1994; Swami et al. 2011; Wood, Douglas, and Sutton 2012; Grzesiak-Feldman 2013; Leander 2014; Uscinski, Klofstad, and Atkinson 2016; Miller, Saunders, and Farhart 2016;

Berinsky 2017). Their work has revealed insights into the cognitive and emotional processes that influence individuals' beliefs in conspiracy theories.

Conspiracy theories have also been a prominent topic of study within communication research, frequently discussed alongside other phenomena like 'fake news,' hate speech, and ideological polarisation (Van Zoonan 2012; Sharma et al., 2017; Benkler et al., 2018; Culloty, 2021). Following this trend in communication research, media studies have also carried out extensive research. Scholars in media studies have examined how changes in communication structures have facilitated the spread of conspiratorial claims, leading to the absence of temporal and spatial constraints in their dissemination (Wood 1982; Pipes 1997; Butter 2014). Additionally, research in journalism has delved into the credibility of conspiratorial journalistic content and its potential disruptions to government systems, political structures, and democracy (Bennett and Livingston, 2018). Recent studies have also investigated the prevalence of mainstream versus conspiratorial content in newspapers (Mompelat et al., 2022).

In recent years, researchers have started examining conspiracy theories from a linguistic standpoint, investigating hate content and aggressiveness in conspiracy-related tweets during COVID-19 through lexicon analysis (Monaci, 2021) and exploring the use of national identity language in association with COVID-19 conspiracy theories (Chen et al., 2022). Comparative analyses of the psychological and linguistic characteristics of conspirators have also been conducted and based on it a tool "ConspiDetector" was developed to detect conspiracies (Giachanou et al., 2023). Moreover, Deutschmann (2020) has offered a unique perspective on identifying conspiracy texts based on facts, semantics, and pragmatic considerations. He found that conspiracies prefer to be complex and involve mysterious cases to attract long term publicity and political actors use it as a scapegoat for undesirable events. Recent works, such as the edited book by Demata et al. (2022), have provided a comprehensive understanding of conspiracies from a discourse perspective by investigating COVID-19 conspiracies. Catenaccio in Demata et al. (2022) investigated the corpus of books that had presented conspiracies related to 9/11 and found three discursive traits; high incidence of meta-discursive references with negatively connotated verbs, the frequent recourse to terms (evidence, facts) and hypothetical structures through "would".

The outbreak of COVID-19 has significantly influenced the landscape of conspiracy research, leading to a plethora of studies focusing on various aspects of COVID-19 related conspiracies. Scholars have investigated the network of COVID-19 conspiracy theories and found that there are organized networks on social media that are manipulating the public opinions through conspiracies (Tangherlini et al., 2020). Uscinski et al. (2020) studied beliefs in COVID-19 theories and reflected that cultural, political, and religious factors have an impact on the beliefs of people, and these beliefs have their impact on COVID-19 control policing (Duffy and Allington, 2020; Monaci, 2021). Li et al. (2020) also studied Chinese social media posts originating in Wuhan City and found that the number of posts increased with the number of posts or vice versa, and this correlation also directed the behaviours of the public towards the causative agent of the disease, changing epidemiological characteristics of the outbreak, public reaction to outbreak control and response measures. Furthermore, studies have explored the emergence of Sinophobic attitudes on social media platforms (Schild et al., 2020). A comprehensive analysis by Marcellino et al. (2021) has categorised various COVID-19 conspiracy theories, providing valuable insights into their diversity and prevalence. The European Commission also listed major conspiracies targeting COVID-19; the virus was artificially created by people with a specific interest, the virus was spread intentionally, or its natural spread artificially augmented to harm as many people as possible, vaccines and cures are intentionally withheld to not disrupt the spread and to harm as many people as possible and certain sanitary measures to counter the spread of the virus are used to

intentionally harm or control society.

With regard to Pakistan, there is minimal research (not relevant to Linguistics) that has presented conspiracies related to COVID-19. However, Khan et al. (2020) presented that people in Pakistan perceive COVID-19 as a grand illusion to target Islamic nations designed to allow Jews to rule the world, to include nano-chips embedded in the bodies of people to gain control through 5G towers, the United States invented the virus in the United Kingdom with subsequent transfer to China for global spread (Khan et al., 2020). The New York Times, in one of the articles, covered the situation of COVID in Pakistan and presented a few conspiracies; politicians are spreading the news of the virus to pocket aid money, a massacre aimed at Iran and Pakistan as they don't accept Greater Israel and God's wrath over women dancing and dressing immodestly (The New York times, 2020). In addition to the previously reported conspiracies, another survey, conducted by Gallup, showed that more than half of the population is unsure if the virus is real and the virus is laboratory-made and spread around the world on purpose (Gallup, 2020).

The above studies highlighted that conspiracies have been studied from diverse perspective and linguistic exploration of conspiracies has started recently. Linguistic studies have focused on finding and analysing conspirated texts from syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, and discourse perspective and found that conspiracies are complex and hard to identify as well as it is less possible to eliminate the phenomenon. However, pragmatic analysis to identify conspiracies is more effective among syntactic, semantic, pragmatic. Later studies have suggested to explore conspirated texts from corpus assisted discourse perspective, but their investigation was restricted to 9/11 and to the texts that were already termed as conspirated. Also, COVI-19 has given rise to the conspiracy research due to the sensitivity of the event and numerous alternate narratives for a single aspect. Therefore, the present research deals with the collecting the data that has one or many conspiracies presented in literature followed by the exploration of lexicon as per corpus assisted discourse analysis perspective.

In conclusion, the reviewed literature provides a comprehensive overview of the diverse research conducted on conspiracy theories, contributing to our understanding of their multifaceted nature and societal impact. The interdisciplinary approach reveals the complexity of conspiracy theories and highlights the need for further investigation in this intriguing field of study.

Theoretical Framework

The preceding linguistic inquiries have predominantly centered on theoretical frameworks encompassing narrative theory, conspiracy theory, cognitive theory, psychoanalytic framework, and digital media. However, it is imperative to further extend these investigations within varying contexts to elucidate the role of language in the propagation of conspiracy narratives. Thus, this research, in conjunction with the work of Catenaccio as explained in Demata et al. (2022), endeavours to scrutinize the utilization of language in the presentation of conspiracy narratives in newspaper opinion articles, utilizing the lens of Corpus Assisted Discourse Analysis (CADA). The following part explains upon the theoretical foundations underpinning the current research.

The terminology CADA of CADS (for present research purposes CADA), denoting Corpus Assisted Discourse Analysis, was originally introduced by Partington (2004) to accommodate the expanding body of research focused on discourse analysis and the integration of techniques from Corpus Linguistics. Broadly, CADA is a offspring of Corpus Linguistics (CL) and draws significant inspiration from the earlier works of Stubbs (1995), Hardt-Mautner (1995), and Krishnamurthy (1996). This section commences by delineating the central concepts and tools employed in corpus-based research, followed by an elucidation of the particularities and principles of CADA.

Corpus Linguistics primarily concerns itself with the examination of language through extensive electronic collections of authentic linguistic data, commonly referred to as corpora (McEnery and Hardie, 2012). These corpora can be expeditiously and reliably queried through specialized corpus-

linguistic software applications, such as AntConc (Anthony, 2011), WordSmith Tools (Scott, 2008), and Sketch Engine (Kilgarriff et al., 2004). While the initial point of analysis often entails statistical outputs, such as frequency lists, corpora can also undergo qualitative scrutiny by studying select excerpts. In essence, CL seeks to investigate both quantitative and qualitative lexical and grammatical patterns across various linguistic varieties (e.g., national varieties like British English), domains (e.g., business communication), or specific genres (e.g., business emails). Insights gleaned from corpus-based research have significantly enhanced our comprehension of language usage, substantiating the existence of regularities and patterns not readily perceptible to the unaided eye. As the pioneer of CL, John Sinclair, aptly observed: "The language looks rather different when you look at a lot of it at once" (Sinclair, 1991, p. 100).

The fundamental tools underpinning much of corpus analysis encompass frequency and keywords, with collocation and concordance constituting the additional two. For the present research, emphasis is placed solely on the former two components. Within the realm of corpus linguistics, frequency denotes the quantification of items within a corpus, whereby an item may be a word, a part of speech, or a keyword. Frequency lists serve as a valuable entry point to a corpus, as they unveil frequently occurring items (located at the top of the list) and infrequent ones (situated toward the list's bottom). High-frequency words often signal discernible regularities, which, in turn, may signify their significance and prominence. Another efficacious method for corpus exploration is the examination of keywords. In Corpus Linguistics, a keyword designates a term that occurs exceptionally frequently in a given corpus in comparison to a typically larger reference corpus (Scott, 2010).

The CADA approach harnesses the quantitative tools furnished by CL, yet it extends the methodological paradigm by incorporating techniques conventionally associated with qualitative discourse analysis to attain a more comprehensive understanding of the discourse in question and its contextual milieu. In addition to frequency and keyword lists, CADA researchers engage with the data through diverse approaches, including close textual analysis, visual examination, or auditory evaluation of select subsets (Partington et al., 2013, p. 12).

The efficacy of the CADA approach is evident in its successful application to investigate a myriad of discourses, encompassing the discourse of science within the British press (Taylor, 2010), the discourse of morality also within the British press (Marchi, 2010), nationalism and language ideologies in the Canadian context (Vessey, 2013), representations of Islam in the British media (Baker et al., 2013), and depictions of immigrants in both the British and Italian press (Taylor, 2014). However, representations of specific events through this methodology have hitherto remained unexplored. Consequently, the ensuing sections present a case study elucidating how the CADA approach can be judiciously employed to scrutinize a corpus containing opinion articles in newspapers that propagate conspiracy narratives.

Methodology

The current study is centred around the compilation and analysis of a corpus of newspaper opinion articles containing COVID-19-related conspiracy theories. This investigation employs a discourse analysis-informed, corpus-based approach. This section provides an intricate overview of the methodology employed in this research. It encompasses the composition of the corpus, the annotation process applied to the corpus, and the subsequent corpus analysis.

Corpus and Corpus Collection

The corpus comprises opinion articles concerning COVID-19, disseminated between January 2020 and April 2020 within the Pakistani newspapers "Dawn" and "The News". To assemble this corpus, a Python data scraping library, newspaper3k, was employed. A sum of 263 opinion articles (137 from "Dawn"

and 126 from "The News") were extracted and stored as distinct files from the two newspapers. These articles encompass a total of 272,679 tokens, with "Dawn" contributing 142,859 tokens and "The News" contributing 129,820 tokens.

Annotation

The annotation was carried out by the researcher. The annotator followed the criteria, if any of the following Conspiracy (derived from previous research and observations) is reflected (implicitly or explicitly) in the opinion article or not:

1. **Origin:** man-made, Chinese bioweapon, Chinese unhygienic conditions or food, a product of the Deep State, a cover-up for 'radiation illnesses' from 5G networks and aliens brought it on earth, invented by US,
2. **Spread:** Only through physical Contact, masks eliminate the spread, aliens are spreading the virus, spread through some device, the Government is spreading it intentionally for taking foreign aid, spreading it with religious targets, and cannot target people who keep them clean.
3. **Controls/Cure:** Social distancing and lockdowns are just useless restrictions, masks cannot protect from virus, lockdowns are by government for making money through fines, restrictions are just to show the world, racist or biased decisions, special tea leaves can cure it, ginger and garlic can cure it and religious recitations can cure it.
4. **Portrayal/Beliefs:** Religious endorsed conspiracies (God's wrath, against Muslims), not a virus only a general flu, already present just newly detected scientifically.

Due to the time constraint, it was not possible to engage and annotate the corpora from the other annotators and calculate inter-annotator agreement. Therefore, all annotations were carried out by the researcher, and it is possible that the results may reflect bias.

Corpus Analysis

To delve into the linguistic aspects of the selected COVID-19-related conspiracy theories, corpus analysis was conducted using Sketch Engine. This tool, recognized for its diverse functionalities, including keyword identification, collocate recognition, topic modeling, and co-occurrence pattern examination, facilitated a thorough investigation of linguistic patterns within the corpus.

To enhance the precision of our analysis, stop words, modal verbs, and discourse markers were excluded. The primary focus of the corpus analysis was directed toward articles identified as containing conspiratorial content through the annotation process. This aligns with our theoretical framework's emphasis on understanding the language used to present and perpetuate conspiracy theories.

Following the quantitative corpus analysis, the research took a qualitative turn, delving into specific instances of conspiracies for in-depth exploration. This qualitative analysis was informed by the theoretical lenses, allowing for a nuanced understanding of how language contributes to the dissemination of COVID-19-related conspiracy theories within newspaper opinion articles.

In summary, the methodology employed in this study is closely aligned with our theoretical framework, allowing us to operationalize our chosen theories (CL and DA) effectively and provide a comprehensive analysis of the role of language in presenting COVID-19-related conspiracy theories.

Results and Discussion

This section provides detailed analysis of both corpora and highlights prominent results as an individual corpus and in comparison, as well.

Annotation Results

After annotating the articles, only 194 articles were identified as presenting any of the above

conspiracies. The statistics are as follows:

Table-1: Annotation Results of Conspiracies in Dawn and The News

	<i>Dawn</i>	<i>The News</i>	<i>Total</i>
Total Number of Conspiracy articles	105	89	194
Origin Related Conspiracies	22	26	48
Spread Related Conspiracies	16	22	38
Control/Cure Related Conspiracies	35	20	55
Portrayal/Beliefs Related Conspiracies	32	21	53

The presented table underscores a notable disparity in the utilization of COVID-19 conspiracies between the two newspapers, "Dawn" and "The News." Specifically, it becomes evident that "Dawn" exhibited a more pronounced inclination toward incorporating such conspiratorial narratives when juxtaposed with "The News." Significantly, the most extensively addressed conspiracy theme, namely "Control/cure," was prominently featured in "Dawn," whereas its prevalence in "The News" was comparatively subdued. Conversely, "The News" prominently focused on conspiracies concerning the virus's origin. Another salient observation within both corpora is the consistency in the utilization of all four types of conspiracies by "The News," as opposed to "Dawn," which displayed a comparatively less uniform engagement with these diverse thematic elements.

Conspiracy Corpus Descriptive Statistics

The below table presents descriptive statistics of conspiracy articles from Dawn and The News.

Table-2: Descriptive Statistics of Conspiracy articles from Dawn and The News

	<i>Items</i>	<i>Dawn</i>	<i>The News</i>
Counts	Tokens	104,565	93,691
	Words	93,543	83,821
	Sentence	4,411	3,945
	Documents	105	89
Lexicon Size	Word	12,068	10,327
	Tag	61	61
	Lempos	9,467	8,071
	Pos	9	9
	Lemma	8,645	7,412
	lc	11,188	9,536

The table above accentuates a parallel trend between the utilization of conspiratorial elements in opinion articles and several linguistic parameters within the "Dawn" newspaper. Notably, "Dawn" has demonstrated a greater employment of tokens, lemma words, and sentences. This phenomenon can potentially be attributed to the variance in the number of articles considered for comparison, contingent on their integration of conspiratorial themes. Conversely, both newspapers exhibit comparable patterns in terms of parts of speech usage and word family utilization. Across all other facets, "Dawn" has demonstrated a discernible advantage over "The News."

Wordlist

The following table presents a wordlist of both corpora parallel to the frequency of each lemma. Top thirty lemmas were selected to understand the choice of frequent words used by both corpora and the orientation of both corpora reflected through words.

Table-3: Wordlist of to 30 lemmas and their frequency in Dawn and The News

<i>Dawn</i>		<i>The News</i>	
<i>Lemma</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Lemma</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
virus	259	people	332
people	248	country	325
world	230	Pakistan	314
government	228	government	287
pandemic	176	Covid-19	259
crisis	176	world	239
Pakistan	174	health	228
country	168	virus	212
health	162	pandemic	190
Covid-19	158	time	189
coronavirus	157	coronavirus	179
social	149	crisis	172
global	139	public	171
economic	129	disease	163
public	119	China	153
lockdown	105	lockdown	152
minister	101	economic	151
number	91	spread	147
state	89	case	134
measure	88	system	130

political	87	human	127
situation	86	global	124
take	85	life	121
system	85	state	120
time	85	good	112
power	81	number	105
spread	81	poor	104
prime	78	Saarc	101
economy	76	worker	87
China	76	fight	96

While the aforementioned table highlights the leading 30 lemmas recurring within both corpora, a pertinent observation emerges: among these 60 lemmas, a mere 16 differ, whereas the remaining 44 are shared across both corpora. Within this set of top 60 lemmas, two salient trends emerge. Firstly, it is evident that both newspapers have extensively covered COVID-19, underscored by the prevalent usage of terms such as "virus," "Covid-19," "health," "pandemic," "coronavirus," "China," "spread," and "crisis." Secondly, distinctive lemmas found in "Dawn," such as "power," "ministers," and "political," suggest a more politically oriented discussion of COVID-19, in contrast to "The News," which approaches the topic from a health-focused perspective, utilizing words like "human," "life," "fight," "good," "poor," and "case."

Multi-Keyword Analysis

The subsequent tables provide an overview of the leading thirty key phrases within both the "Dawn" and "The News" corpora, aligned with their respective frequencies in the corpora, as well as their frequency in the reference corpora (ENGLISH WEB 2021 - ENTENTEN21) and their corresponding scores. Analogous to the approach with lemmas in the wordlist, the selection of these top thirty key phrases aims to illuminate the prevalent choices of frequently used key phrases in both corpora. Moreover, this analysis sheds light on the overarching thematic orientations manifested within these corpora through the deployment of these phrases.

Table-4: Top 30 Multi-Keyword List in Dawn

<i>Dawn</i>					
<i>Item</i>	<i>F(foc)</i>	<i>F(ref)</i>	<i>RF(foc)</i>	<i>RF(ref)</i>	<i>Score</i>
soft power	23	27636	220.0	0.45	152.52
prime minister imran khan	15	6006	143.5	0.10	131.62
sindh government	14	2846	133.9	0.05	128.93
spread of the virus	23	47502	220.0	0.77	124.74
spanish flu	14	16328	133.9	0.27	106.62

provincial government	29	104583	277.3	1.70	103.16
tableeghi jamaat	10	334	95.6	0.01	96.113
health emergency	14	54815	133.9	0.89	71.367
murad ali shah	7	113	66.9	0.00	67.82
deadly virus	9	18398	86.1	0.30	67.043
healthcare system	20	117913	191.3	1.91	65.967
un secretary	7	2381	66.9	0.04	65.415
imran khan	8	16225	76.5	0.26	61.346
hand sanitiser	8	17799	76.5	0.29	60.129
daily wage	7	11332	66.9	0.18	57.385
populist leader	6	3375	57.4	0.05	55.347
social distancing	35	313671	334.7	5.09	55.097
death toll	18	133175	172.1	2.16	54.75
chief minister	20	159950	191.3	2.60	53.45
community worker	6	8965	57.4	0.15	50.962
un secretary general	6	9378	57.4	0.15	50.665
health infrastructure	6	11569	57.4	0.19	49.148
online teaching	7	24513	66.9	0.40	48.6
muslim country	9	49744	86.1	0.81	48.166
debt write-off	5	1025	47.8	0.02	48.018
punjab government	6	14154	57.4	0.23	47.471
prime minister	76	887373	726.8	14.41	47.234
other muslim country	5	2497	47.8	0.04	46.915
global flow	5	2624	47.8	0.04	46.822
complete lockdown	5	2936	47.8	0.05	46.596

Table-5: Top 30 Multi-Keyword List in The News

<i>The News</i>					
<i>Item</i>	<i>F(foc)</i>	<i>F(ref)</i>	<i>RF(foc)</i>	<i>RF(ref)</i>	<i>Score</i>
saarc summit	14	1451	149.4	0.02	146.965
infected person	18	23006	192.1	0.37	140.599
sindh government	13	2846	138.8	0.05	133.581
public health system	15	17845	160.1	0.29	124.908
healthcare system	31	117913	330.9	1.91	113.866
imran khan	12	16225	128.1	0.26	102.165
spread of the disease	12	17651	128.1	0.29	100.326
testing kit	11	17035	117.4	0.28	92.752
health security	10	9988	106.7	0.16	92.7

relief package	11	18106	117.4	0.29	91.505
provincial government	23	104583	245.5	1.70	91.354
spread of the virus	15	47502	160.1	0.77	90.95
saarc member	8	539	85.4	0.01	85.638
black swan	12	32471	128.1	0.53	84.519
community with a shared future	8	1494	85.4	0.02	84.341
novel coronavirus	16	66380	170.8	1.08	82.669
complete lockdown	8	2936	85.4	0.05	82.456
health crisis	19	95919	202.8	1.56	79.686
social distancing	45	313671	480.3	5.09	78.99
health system	34	226058	362.9	3.67	77.912
shared future	8	6967	85.4	0.11	77.608
shared future for mankind	7	983	74.7	0.02	74.524
future for mankind	7	1480	74.7	0.02	73.937
global public health	8	11487	85.4	0.19	72.807
lethal disease	7	2753	74.7	0.04	72.474
covid-19 crisis	16	87530	170.8	1.42	70.944
protective gear	9	25618	96.1	0.42	68.547
franchised wisdom	6	0	64.0	0.00	65.04
under-trial prisoner	6	280	64.0	0.00	64.746
passive immunization	6	1024	64.0	0.02	63.977

The aforementioned tables showcase multi-word terms extracted from distinct corpora. Echoing the trend in the wordlist, the preeminent terms within the "Dawn" corpus reveal a pronounced political inclination. Notable phrases such as "prime minister," "provincial government," "social distancing," and "soft power" emerge with the highest frequencies. It's worth noting, however, that the cumulative frequency pattern signifies a prevailing emphasis on health-related themes. In contrast, the "The News" corpus aligns with its wordlist's focus on health perspectives, evident in phrases like "social distancing," "health system," "healthcare system," and "provincial government." While these phrases might not unequivocally denote specific COVID-19 categories or theories, certain expressions like "provincial government," "passive immunization," "tableeghi jammat," "complete lockdown," "spread of the disease," "Spanish flu," and "hand sanitizer" subtly allude to conspiracy theories.

From the above results, it becomes apparent that readers of "Dawn" exhibit a greater proclivity toward engaging with conspiracy-related information, primarily with the intent to critique or challenge governmental and political structures. A parallel trend was previously observed by researchers in the field of journalism (Bennett and Livingston, 2018). Additionally, in tandem with its political orientation, "Dawn" maintains a focus on healthcare matters. In this aspect, similar to the study conducted by Mompelat et al. (2022), "Dawn" endeavours to rationalize its conspiracy narratives by drawing comparisons to mainstream content.

Although the results from corpus analysis does not reflect the type of conspiracy theory present in the newspaper opinion article. However, following examples depict the use of conspiracies in the newspaper opinion articles:

Example-1: The below example attempts to enlighten the readers about the possible conspiracies related to the origin of COVID-19:

“Many scientists trying to pinpoint the origin of this virus have concluded that it was caused by bats from a certain cave in Hubei province. From them it appears to have jumped to civet cats kept in small cages in the seafood market at Wuhan by way of urine or faeces. Some biologists conjecture that the outbreak was caused by snakes.”

In the provided excerpt, the utilization of the term "conjecture" in the closing sentence carries notable significance. Its inclusion indicates that the author isn't asserting the statement as an established fact, but rather as a plausible hypothesis. This nuanced choice is crucial as it acknowledges the prevailing uncertainty regarding the genesis of COVID-19. Additionally, the term "appears" employed in the second sentence imparts that there exists some substantiating evidence for the assertion that the virus leaped to civet cats, though this evidence is not definitively conclusive.

Furthermore, the passage effectively employs impartial and neutral language to impartially introduce various conspiracy theories. Noteworthy words such as "concluded," "jumped," and "conjecture" signal varying degrees of certainty or speculation. This strategic diction is influenced by the structure typical of opinion articles and journalistic writing, where authors strive to deliberate on diverse viewpoints and empower readers to formulate their perspectives grounded in their cultural, social, and historical contexts.

Example-2: The below text also attempts to present a conspiracy related to the COVID-19's origin:

“Whatever the cause, it is certain that China's food preferences have triggered this plague.”

The provided passage commences with the phrase "Whatever the cause," which conveys an underlying uncertainty on the author's part concerning the origin of COVID-19. Subsequently, the author asserts with confidence that China's culinary choices are undeniably responsible for sparking the virus. The narrative embraces an origin-centric conspiracy theory, positing that China's dietary preferences directly instigated COVID-19. This claim bears substantial gravity, thus warranting meticulous examination of the supporting evidence. Concurrently, it's vital to contextualize the text's genre, identified as an opinion article. In this context, it can be inferred that the article has already delved into potential causative factors, thereby enabling readers to form their interpretations and, eventually, allowing the author to articulate their own stance.

Example-3: The following excerpt presents a conspiracy related to the COVID-19's control/cure:

“In the wake of the coronavirus outbreak, Asian people living in Europe and the US already report facing discrimination.”

The utilization of the phrase "facing discrimination" alongside the term "Asian" within the text signals a contemplation of conspiracies intertwined with issues of racial and ethnic bias, particularly in the context of managing COVID-19. These contentions shed light on significant allegations aimed at the US and Europe, suggesting the presence of discriminatory policies that disproportionately affect individuals from diverse ethnic backgrounds.

Example-4: The following example presents a conspiracy related to the COVID-19's portrayal/beliefs:

“The commonly held perceptions that COVID-19 is similar to the common flu.”

The statement "COVID-19 is similar to the common flu" resonates with the dissemination of a conspiracy theory that concerns beliefs surrounding the nature of COVID-19. This proposition diverges

from the factual reality, given that the common flu is comparatively less severe, less contagious, and results in fewer fatalities in contrast to COVID-19. Moreover, the inclusion of the phrase "commonly held perceptions" suggests a prevalence of this unfounded perspective among a considerable number of individuals. This choice of wording hints at the author's subtle inclination to indirectly advocate their own standpoint on the matter. It is notable that readers could potentially be swayed by the latter phrase alone, leading them to form the perception that COVID-19 is akin to the common flu, underscoring the influence of the writer's perspective on the readers' interpretation.

A crucial factor that surfaces within the realm of newspaper opinions pertains to the inherent nature of the genre itself. Given that opinions inherently engage with diverse viewpoints, it becomes quite conceivable that many opinion articles could inadvertently assume the guise of conspiracy theories. In light of this, it becomes imperative to establish a clear understanding of what constitutes a conspiracy and to establish definitive criteria to discern and classify newspaper opinion articles accordingly. This endeavour is essential to ensure a judicious differentiation between genuine discussions of varied perspectives and the potential inclination towards conspiratorial content.

Conclusion

In this study, an exploration of newspaper opinion articles pertaining to COVID-19 conspiracies has illuminated several significant insights. The methodology employed, incorporating discourse analysis-informed corpus investigation, facilitated a comprehensive examination of the textual landscape. The presented findings underscore the nuanced interplay between linguistic choices and the underlying intents of these articles.

The analysis revealed a multifaceted orientation within the "Dawn" and "The News" corpora, encapsulating political and health perspectives, respectively. While both newspapers tackled the COVID-19 crisis extensively, "Dawn" showcased a marked propensity for political discourse, critiquing governmental structures and systems. On the other hand, "The News" exhibited a predominant focus on health-related discussions, reflecting the challenges and considerations within the healthcare sector.

Notably, the research illuminated the intricate dynamic between language and intent, as evinced by the careful selection of terms such as "conjecture" and "appears." These nuanced choices highlight the authors' recognition of the uncertainty inherent in the origin of COVID-19 and the multifaceted nature of its causative factors.

Moreover, the research emphasized the role of opinion articles as platforms for exploring diverse perspectives, even including conspiracy theories. The measured presentation of differing viewpoints allows readers to interpret information within their unique contexts, fostering a dynamic interaction between journalism and readership.

This research contributes to a richer understanding of the ways language, intent, and genre intersect within the context of COVID-19 conspiracy theories in newspaper opinion articles. It underscores the importance of critically evaluating language choices, considering genre implications, and recognizing the inherent complexity of interpreting multifaceted issues like COVID-19 within the realm of journalism. However, limited data and specific time orientation make it difficult to generalize the results at the larger scale.

Recommendations

- Further research, encompassing a larger dataset and an extended timeframe, is imperative to yield more definitive and representative outcomes.

- Calculating inter-annotator agreement is necessary to mitigate potential researcher bias.
- Subsequent investigations could involve more expansive research, aimed at precisely delineating conspiratorial elements within journalistic compositions, where authors often engage with diverse viewpoints.
- Linguists possess the opportunity to delve deeper into the intricacies of conspiratorial language, enabling a clearer demarcation between the language employed in conspiracy and non-conspiracy texts.

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